

Paper 17

AWARENESS AMONG B.ED TEACHER TRAINEES TOWARDS CYBER-CRIME-A STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In present scenario, information and communication technologies are universal and digitalization in all areas is expanding and the world of internet today has become a parallel form of life and living. The usage of Internet is one of the fastest-growing areas (Miao Y., 2007) and the ICTs is a foundation for development in the creation, and use of network-based services. The introduction of ICTs into many aspects of everyday life has led to the development of the modern concept of the information society as it offers great opportunities. Online banking and shopping, the use of mobile data services and voice over Internet protocol telephony are just some examples of how far the integration of ICTs into our daily lives and education system. Online web representation is nowadays more important for businesses than printed publicity materials and Internet-based communication and phone services are growing faster than landline communications (Zittrain, 2006). But on the other side, the growth of the information society is accompanied by new and serious threats too, like different forms crime committed or facilitated via the Internet, may be termed as cybercrime.

The present study was carried out with the objective to investigate the awareness level of BEd Teacher Trainees on cybercrime. The study was carried out on 100 B.Ed. Teacher Trainees. Cybercrime awareness scale constructed and validated by Rajasekar S. (2011) was administered to collect the data. The obtained data were analyzed by using mean, S.D. and t-test. Analysis of the results revealed, no significant difference towards cybercrime awareness among BEd teacher trainees in terms of their locality and streams opted. Majority of the BEd teacher trainees fall under moderate or average level of cybercrime awareness (60%). None of the BEd teacher trainees fall under excellent level of cybercrime awareness (0%), 18% of the BEd teacher trainees exhibited below average level of cybercrime awareness and 16% of the BEd teacher trainees shown low level of cybercrime awareness. A small percentage of BEd teacher trainees (4%) and

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(2%) fell in the category of above average and high level of cybercrime awareness.

1.0.0 Introduction

Internet, though offers prodigious advantage to society, also present opportunities for crime using new and highly sophisticated technology tools. Today e-mail and websites have become the preferred means of communication. Organizations provide internet access to their staff and it, facilitate almost instant exchange and dissemination of data, images and variety of teaching learning material. This includes not only educational and informative material but also information that might be undesirable or anti-social. Cybercrime is a term used to broadly describe criminal activity in which computers or computer networks are a tool, or a place of criminal activity. It is also used to include traditional crimes in which computers or networks are used to enable the criminal activity.

1.1.0 Need for the study:

In teaching-learning process, the use of internet is inevitable. The importance of e-learning is increasing day by day. This is all because of distance learning and searching and sharing of study materials on internet. Besides it, internet provides many search engines that helps a student as well as a teacher to find out the solutions of their problems. It also helps a teacher and student to update their knowledge by getting the new information about new researches, new techniques etc. A teacher and a student can also get connected outside the class-room through the internet. And when they get the benefits of internet then of course they should face the risk factors also attached to it.

Hence, the awareness on cybercrime is very much needed for the learners and also for teachers, so that they can prevent to face the unexpected problems or cybercrimes such as hacking, phishing, spam, computer viruses, sabotage, wire fraud, ATM fraud, internet fraud, identity theft etc. and they can take the appropriate measures to sort out these problems. Awareness about cybercrimes will also help in decreasing the involvement of the students or our coming generations in cybercrimes. This study will help to find out the awareness level among B.Ed teacher trainees of D.K district. And after knowing their awareness level, they can take further steps to increase their level of cybercrime awareness. It will be beneficial for themselves and their teaching career and also, they can aware their students about cybercrimes.

1.2.0 Statement of the Problem: A study on Awareness among B.Ed teacher trainees towards Cyber-crime.

1.3.0 Operational definitions of the terms

Cybercrime: Cybercrime is a term used to broadly describe criminal activity in which computers or computer networks are a tool, or a place of criminal activity and include everything from electronic cracking to denial-of-service attacks.

Cybercrime has been used to describe a wide range of offences, including offences against computer data and systems (such as “hacking”), computer-related forgery and fraud (such as “phishing”), content offences (such as disseminating child pornography), and copyright offences (such as the dissemination of pirated content).

In the present study, the awareness level of cybercrime among BEd teacher trainees was measured.

Teacher Trainees: Teacher trainees are the students who are studying in the teacher training courses i.e. B.Ed, and M.Ed. In the present study the term teacher trainees’ stands for the student-teachers of the B.Ed. Course.

1.4.0 Objectives of the study

- a) To study the awareness level of cybercrime among BEd teacher trainees of Mangaluru taluk
- b) To study the difference in the cybercrime awareness of Science and Arts BEd teacher trainees of Mangaluru taluk
- c) To study the difference in the cybercrime awareness among Urban and Rural BEd teacher trainees of Mangaluru taluk

1.5.0 Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant difference between Science and Arts BEd teacher trainees in terms of Cybercrime awareness

H₀2: There is no significant difference between Urban and Rural BEd teacher trainees in terms of Cybercrime awareness

1.6.0 Methodology

The present study was a descriptive survey study. In order to meet the objectives of the study, the

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investigator had selected the single variable namely cybercrime awareness.

1.6.1 Population: The population for the study includes the all B.Ed. Teacher Trainees of D.K district.

1.6.2 Sample: The sample consisted of 90 teacher trainees from Srinivas university college of education, Mangaluru taluk.

1.7.0 Tool: Cyber Crime Awareness among B.Ed. Teacher Trainees was measured by Cyber Crime Awareness Scale (CCAS-RS) developed by Dr. S. Rajasekar. It comprised a total of 23 questions and was divided into two parts. The first part consisted of four demographic and background questions and the second part consisted of 23 close ended statements about students’ cybercrime awareness, which were rated on a five-point Likert scale, with one indicating “strongly disagree” and five indicating “strongly agree.” The statements covered the following two areas: (1) cybercrime awareness, which included statements dealing with knowledge about cybercrime and whether the participants were trying to protect themselves from it; and (2) being a victim of a cybercrime, which examined whether the participants had been a victim of a cybercrime.

1.8.0 Statistical Techniques used: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test was employed to measure Cyber Crime Awareness among BEd teacher trainees.

1.9 Analysis of the objectives

1.9.1: Analysis of objective One - The first objective was to study the awareness level of cybercrime among BEd teacher trainees of Mangaluru taluk.

The following table shows the frequencies of the scores of awareness of cybercrime among BEd teacher trainees

Table1.1: showing the frequencies of the scores of awareness of cybercrime among BEd teacher trainees

Levels	Number of teacher trainees	Awareness level of Cybercrime in Percentage
Excellent	0	0
High	2	2%
Above Average	4	4%
Average	54	60%
Below Average	16	18%
Low	14	16%
Total	90	100%

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Figure 1.1: Pie chart showing the percentages of frequencies of scores of Awareness level of Cybercrime among BEd teacher trainees

The Table 1.1 and Figure 1.1 reveals that majority of BEd teacher trainees shows moderate or average level of cybercrime awareness (60%). None of the BEd teacher trainees fall under excellent level of cybercrime awareness (0%), 18% of the BEd teacher trainees exhibited below average level of cybercrime awareness and 16% of the BEd teacher trainees shown low level of cybercrime awareness. A small percentage of BEd teacher trainees (4%) and (2%) fell in the category of above average and high level of cybercrime awareness.

1.9.2 Analysis of objective Two - To study the difference in the awareness level of cybercrime of Science and Arts BEd teacher trainees of Mangaluru taluk

The following table shows the frequencies of the scores of awareness level of cybercrime of Science and Arts BEd teacher trainees

Table 1.2: Number (N), Mean (M), Standard Deviation (S.D), and ‘t’ value of the awareness level of cybercrime of Science and Arts BEd teacher trainees

Stream	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Significance
Science	45	71.28889	7.066638	0.49	Not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level
Arts	45	70.53333	6.66265		

As the above table 1.2 indicates, the ‘t’ value between the two means of two variables is found to be 0.49, which is lesser than the table value (), which is not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level

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of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference towards Cyber Crime Awareness among Science and Arts teacher trainees” was accepted. Hence, The mean of Science BEd teacher trainees was 71.29 which is higher than the mean of Arts BEd teacher trainees 70.53. It can be interpreted that Science BEd teacher trainees has more awareness towards cybercrime than Arts BEd teacher trainees.

1.9.3 Analysis of objective Three- To study the difference in the awareness level of cybercrime of Urban and Rural BEd teacher trainees of Mangaluru taluk

The following table shows the frequencies of the scores of awareness level of cybercrime of Urban and Rural BEd teacher trainees

Table 1.3: Number (N), Mean (M), Standard Deviation (S.D), and ‘t’ value of the awareness level of cybercrime of Urban and Rural BEd teacher trainees

Stream	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Significance
Urban	36	70.28	7.14	1.02	Not significant 0.01 and 0.05 level
Rural	54	71.81	6.75		

The Table 1.3 reveals that ‘t’ value is 1.02 which is not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference towards Cyber Crime Awareness among Urban and Rural BEd teacher trainees” was accepted.

Major Findings of the study

1. Majority of the BEd teacher trainees have moderate or average level of cybercrime awareness (60%). None of the BEd teacher trainees fall under excellent level of cybercrime awareness (0%), 18% of the BEd teacher trainees exhibited below average level of cybercrime awareness and 16% of the BEd teacher trainees shown low level of cybercrime awareness. A small percentage of BEd teacher trainees (4%) and (2%) fell in the category of above average and high level of cybercrime awareness.
2. There is no significant difference towards cybercrime awareness among Science and Arts BEd teacher trainees. BEd Science teacher trainees has more awareness towards cybercrime than Arts BEd teacher trainees.
3. There is no significant difference towards cybercrime awareness among Urban and Rural

BEd teacher trainees.

1.10.0 Educational implications of the study:

The result of the study can be usefully employed in school practice. The present study has the following educational implications for the school teachers, and students:

- a. It can help the teacher trainees to know about the level of cybercrime awareness.
- b. The teacher trainees need to be trained about safe internet browsing and protect themselves of being victims.
- c. The educational department and other concerned departments need to organize workshops or seminars to the teacher trainees on awareness regarding ‘cybercrime and its harmful effects among school children and teenagers’. Thus, they can guide their students about the same and it will help in decreasing the involvement of students in cybercrimes who do mistakes due to the lack of awareness towards cybercrime.
- d. Teacher education curriculum may include this topic, so that they will learn it compulsorily. Thus all the teacher trainees gain the knowledge as a foundation and basic information.
- e. Although information technology is widely used at higher educational institutions, cyberspace security topics need to be taught to all students across the board in order to increase their cybercrime awareness and to prevent them from becoming victims of cybercrime. It is vital that students in higher education develop a deeper understanding of cyber risks and a set of skills to mitigate these.
- f. The number of cybercrime victims could be reduced by introducing proper awareness activities such as training programs, sufficient resource for compliance, develop policies & regulations and sufficient protection of personal information (Bougaardt and Kyobe, 2011). Choi (2008) emphasizes on the effectiveness of university programs in promoting knowledge and values about cybercrime as these programs could improve future behaviour of students and teachers towards cybercrime in terms of safety and security.

1.11.0 Limitations of the study

- d. This study can be applied on a large sample of young adults or teacher trainees or teachers of government and private schools.
- e. The study can be applied on a large sample of teacher trainees of rural and urban localities.
- f. Future researchers could also focus on developing strategies to increase the level of cybercrime awareness and to alert students to the risks of being victims of cybercrimes.
